

Lake Kivu (Albertine Rift) Proximity and Incidence of Cholera at Katana Rural Health Zone

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this work is to determine the impact of cholera risk linked to proximity of the Lake Kivu. Data were collected at the first semester of 2012 in the Rural Health Zone of Katana, coupled with household interviews. Cholera cases reported at the hospital from 2002 to 2011 at the centre for cholera treatment of Katana Rural health zone were collected, coupled with household interviews. During this decade, It was found that the weekly cholera incidence was two folds in the sites in the nearby of the lake then the ones in the mainland ($P < 0.001$). Indeed, the survey revealed that in the Health zone of Katana, proximity to the lake exposes households to cholera two folds than in the mainland (OR= 2,05 ; IC: 1,0913-3,8762; $P=0,025$) and the consumption of the water from the lake increases the risk from a factor 12 (OR=12 ; IC 95%: 4.365-33.131; $P=0.000$).

Keyword: Lake Kivu proximity, cholera risk, Katana health zone.

INTRODUCTION:

Cholera is a diarrhea affection of epidemic character caused by a bacterium, *Vibrio cholera* or type 01 or 0139. This disease is mainly found in very poor areas living in insalubrious areas with high population density, without clean water or adequate health infrastructures, mostly in the periphery of urban areas in developing countries [1-3].

Since Cholera appeared in 1817 in the Gulf of Bengale at India, the world count today seven pandemic cholera, only the 7th reached sub-Sahara Africa. Known since 1961 in the Celebes Islands in Indonesia, the 7th cholera pandemic reached the eastern Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) from Kalemie (Katanga Province) through Tanzania and the whole of the Albertine Rift was infected: the entire Kivu province and Burundi in July 1978, Rwanda in August 1978 [4]. The region has become since, one of active zones of cholera occurrence with 20 % of cases reported officially in the world to World Health Organization (WHO) between 1999 and 2008 [5].

The first reports of cholera in the nearby of Lake Kivu (1978) were in Ibindja island (Katana health zone), which in a few weeks reached 4500 cases of which, 145 died. Cities of Goma (North Kivu) and Bukavu (South Kivu) were also reached [6]. These areas are part of the seven zones of high risk of the cholera epidemic identified in the DRC by Bompangue et al [7], all of them, at lake shores. This has led to suspicions on the presence of organisms meant to be reservoirs of choleric vibrio in the lakes.

Thus, the proximity to the lake has been said to be a factor exposing to cholera risk. Since, very few studies dealt with this to confirm the hypothesis even though in continental Africa, many studies took place in the seashore. The scarce studies in the DRC [8, 9] cover a large area, which complicates the understanding of

the results. Other investigations by Bompangue [10], Katana and Bukavu were taken together while the two sites are far one from the other: Katana is a rural health zone while Bukavu is an urban zone. It is therefore possible that etiology of cholera might be different in both sites. Indeed, the urgency of intervention for water and sanitation by the NGO Action Against Hunger (ACF) between June and December 2010 in health zones often victims of cholera epidemic, even though it gave good result at Bukavu, led to the increase of the occurrence of cholera at Katana [11]. The specificity of our methods to circumscribe investigations to at fine scale is to provide information on susceptible to improve the level of understanding of the problem.

The Rural Health Zone of Katana is appropriate for these kinds of studies: emergence of cholera in Lake Kivu [6], half of the health zone is located at the lake shore (Figure 1) and nine of its 17 health centres are located entirely or in part near the lake. Socio-demographic conditions of inhabitants are homogenous and most of them depend on the lake for their needs in water [11]. Each year, there are reports of cholera to WHO since more than a decade [7].

This paper aims to contribute to the understanding of the etiology of cholera in the African great lake region in order to improve strategies against the disease. So, we plan to obtain the temporal and spatial profile of the cholera incidence in Katana rural health Zone and to determine the role of Lake Kivu in the occurrence of cholera.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study is retrospective and deals with cases of cholera that reported to the CTC (Cholera Treatment Centre) at the Katana rural health zone from January 2002 to December 2011. To elucidate cholera cases linked with utilization of water from Lake Kivu, we conducted a survey since February 2012 until May 2012 on a random sample of 400 households, of which 200 from the nine health center at lakeshore and 200 from the remaining 8 health centers at mainland. The sample size was calculated using the software Epi Info 6, confidence interval of 95 %. Only adults were interviewed to the questionnaire after a brief explanation of the aims of the census.

Figure 1. Map of Lake Kivu and location of Katana Rural Health zone

The dependent variables are; the distribution of cholera cases (retrospective data) and the frequency of cholera in the households (the survey). The households considered as being often victims of cholera are the ones having recorded an episode of cholera for at least 2 years between 2009 and 2011. In Katana rural health zone, cholera cases are detected by considering clinical definition of the WHO Stipulating that: " in not epidemic period it is about a sick person of more than five years old suffering from an aqueous diarrhea (generally with vomiting) causing a severe dehydration In epidemic period, it is about a sick person of more than two years old suffering from an acute aqueous diarrhea in a region where rages an epidemic of cholera " [12]. Biological confirmation is made only on some first cases at the beginning of the epidemics.

We attempted to obtain information on where they get drinking water, situation of the sanitation, hygiene of water and hygienic condition of hands. For this study, good fecal hygiene means presence of clean sanitary; good water hygiene means treatment of water drinking at the house; good hygiene of hands means a correct wash hands before eating and after exit sanitary. Data were analyzed using Excel, Epi Info 3.5.4 and SPSS. ANOVA test and logistic regression allowed getting the independent factors significantly affecting the causal factor.

RESULTS

Spatio temporal distribution of cholera at Katana: 2002-2011

From January 1st 2002 to 31st December 2011, Katana rural health zone recorded 3651 cholera cases of which 1034 from areas far from the lake and 2617 cases in areas close to the lake. The trend of annual cases given in Figure 2 shows an important variability between years. During the decade investigated each year, areas near the lake present more cases of cholera than the ones far from the lake.

Figure 2. Distribution of cholera's cases according to years and to lake's positioning at Katana health zone, from 2002 until 2011

Data in table 1 show that in Katana health zone, the areas close to the lake have more than the double of cholera cases as compared to those far from the lake (5.1 cases against 1.8); and also, the difference of weekly means between both categories of health areas is highly significant (P = 0.000).

Tableau 1: ANOVA test of the variability of weekly incidence means of cholera from 2002 until 2011 between health areas in lake shore and those far from the lake

Location	Mean	N	Ecart-type
Lake shore	5.119	520	8.884
Far from the lake	1.869	520	3.318
<i>Anova*Kruskall-Wallis</i>	(H) = 53.016	df=1	P=0.000***

Hygiene practices, water consumption and risk of cholera in Katana rural health zone

Results of the interview conducted are in Figure 3 which shows that 59 % of households are frequently cholera victim. The rate is 75 % in areas close to the lake and 41 % in areas far from the lake. Hygienic practices in Katana are very poor and, are similar in the whole health zone. More than 90 % of households interviewed have poor practices of hygiene for hands and faecal hygiene, and 82.5 % are poor for the water hygiene.

Figure 3. Relative frequency of households in Katana health Zone for hand washing, faecal hygiene, water consumption and cholera outbreak

When considering water consumption, the situation changes according to the proximity to the lake: 72.5 % of households use water from the lake (while 12.5 % of households far from the lake use it), than 9 % uses water from streams (against 50.5 % of households far from the lake) and 18.5 % use tap water (against 37 % of households far from the lake).

From this study, the regression test revealed that the water consumption, hygiene of hands, hygiene of water, faecal hygiene and proximity to the lake had significant links with cholera episodes in households ($p < 0.05$). After the multivariate regression analysis, (Table 2), only water hygiene, the proximity to the lake and water consumption have significant links with cholera episodes, the last one has highly significant links ($p < 0.001$). However, only proximity to the lake and consumption of water from the lake has an $OR > 1$.

Table 2 : Results of analyses of links between cholera risks of households at Katana Rural Health Zone and different factors investigated using multivariate logistic regression

Variables	OR	Confidence interval 95%	Z-Statistics	p-value
Health area close to lake	2.057	1.091-3.876	2.230	0.026*
Water hygiene	0.405	0.187-0.874	-2.300	0.021*
Hand hygiene	0.582	0.078-4.356	-0.526	0.599
Faecal hygiene	0.508	0.056-4.636	-0.600	0.549
Consumption water from lake	12.026	4.365-33.131	9.264	0.000***

DISCUSSION

This work examines the role played by Lake Kivu in the distribution of cholera incidence in the health zone of Katana from 2002 to 2011 revealed significant differences ($p=0.000$) of cholera occurrence according to the location of the site explored (lake shore or far from the lake).

Indeed, the average weekly incidence was twofold more important in the lake shore than in areas far from the lake (Table 1). These results at fine scale corroborate with those obtained by Bompangue countrywide. The later author found a positive correlation between the proximity to the lake and vulnerability to cholera [10]. Thus, from the 11 provinces of the DRC, cholera is present in 3 provinces (Katanga, South Kivu and North Kivu) that are located at the shore of some of the great lakes of the East African Rift, with more cases in South Kivu province [10, 13]. At the contrary, in the urban Ibanda Health Zone at Bukavu, where some health areas which are close to the lake are urbanised and have potable water, no cholera case has been found in the proximity of the lake during the same decade of these investigations [3]. These contrasting results leading to an increase of cholera cases in our results (at lake shore) can be explained by the fact that these populations use the water from the lake for all usages even for drinking (Figure 3, Table 2).

Of the exposition parameters investigated, only the lake proximity ($OR= 2.05$; $IC: 1.091-3.876$; $P=0.025$) and lake water consumption ($OR=12$; $IC : 95\%: 4.365-33.131$; $P=0.000$) were determinant variables for cholera in the Katana health zone. These results are in agreement with those found by Birmingham and al. [14] at Rumonge (Burundi) in the neighbourhood of Lake Tanganyika. They found a link between cholera occurrence and the proximity of the lake as well as lake water consumption. Our results show that at Katana, the consumption of lake water exposes populations 12 folds to cholera. The hypothesis of an

aquatic reservoir of choleric vibrio in this lacustrine ecosystem is increasingly envisaged. Lake Kivu surface waters, with a pH between 8 and 9, temperatures ranging between 23 and 25° C [15, 16], and the predominance of copepods in its zooplankton community [17] offers a good environment for choleric vibrio [18-21].

Besides, the trend of annual cases given in Figure 2 shows an important variability between years which can be consecutive to variations of trophic conditions in the Lake Kivu. In fact, from 2002 till 2005, year 2003 present the highest number of cholera cases. During the same period, similar results were found by Isumbusho [17] for zooplankton abundance and copepod rate in zooplankton community of Lake Kivu. It is possible that, as in Bangladesh [22, 23], copepods, dominant micro – crustaceans in Lake Kivu are hosts of the pathogen choleric vibrio in this fresh water ecosystem. The increase of zooplankton may favour that of cholera vibrio could result in the increase of cases.

Even though lacustrine ecosystems are different from estuarine waters; the best biotopes for *Vibrio cholerae* [22], these results reveal that the hypothesis according to which Lake Kivu is a reservoir of choleric vibrio, cholera pathogen, this can be possible even though its presence at long-term has not been proved in this east African great lake. More studies are needed to elucidate the role of Lake Kivu in the persistence of cholera in its shores.

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